

THE MORAL CONCEPTS OF "GOOD" AND "EVIL" ARE THE MAIN INDICATORS OF HUMAN MORALITY

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Annotation: In this article, the study of the nature of "good" and "evil" has been a topic of study by philosophers, scientists and researchers for centuries, and that "evil" and "good" as moral concepts are closely related but opposing concepts. . It is noted that some examples of discussions about the concepts of "good" and "bad" are also given.

Key words: good, evil, good, evil, concept, morality, meaning, essence, norm, philosopher.

We use the terms "good"/"bad" or "good"/"bad" in everyday speech without thinking deeply about their meaning. These concepts are the most generalized forms of moral assessment in life and serve to distinguish between moral and immoral things.

Over the centuries, the concepts of "good" and "evil" have become widespread. Although they are not personal in nature, they play a key role in matters of morality. As noted, the study of the nature of "good" and "evil" has been the subject of study by philosophers, scientists and researchers for centuries. "Evil" as a moral concept is essentially the opposite of "good."

In a broad sense, "evil" includes all actions that are contrary to public moral norms and deserve harsh criticism and condemnation. On the contrary, the concept of "good" is closely related to the concept of kindness, which indicates a positive characteristic of a person, his high moral value. The concept of "good" includes everything that helps satisfy the spiritual and material needs of a person. These include natural resources, education, and various cultural artifacts. But it should be noted that useful does not always equal good. For example, art does not serve any utilitarian (practical) purpose, but it is very important. On the other hand, industrial development is pushing humanity to the bottom of environmental destruction[1].

The concept of wellness is a form of mental well-being. In a moral sense, this concept is often used as a substitute for the word "good." "Good" refers to the most general interests, aspirations - what should be in life and what is worthy of approval. Modern ethics defines the concept of goodness in different but interrelated aspects. Including: 1) kindness is a characteristic of a certain

action; 2) a set of positive moral norms; 3) the moral purpose of the action; 4) the moral attribute of faith.

Philosophy emphasizes that the concepts of “good” and “evil” are closely related to each other. There is no absolute good or absolute evil. In every bad act there is at least a small particle of good, in every good there is an element of evil. He can also reverse "good" and "bad". For example, in Sparta, newborn children with physical disabilities were thrown into the abyss. In Japan, old and helpless people were once taken alive to the “valley of death.” What is now called barbarism was once considered a good deed. Even today, some actions can be considered both bad and good at the same time. It directly depends on the situation. For example, if a police officer kills a murderer in a series of shootouts, then killing the criminal is considered "good."

“Evil” is also a moral category and is the opposite of “good.” It summarizes various opinions about immoral acts, as well as vices that cause harm to other people. These actions and qualities deserve moral criticism. “Evil” is everything that is contrary to the good of society and the individual: disease, racism, bureaucracy, various crimes, chauvinism, alcoholism, drug addiction, etc.

That is why the discussion about the concepts of “good” and “bad” is one of the most important issues. Friedrich Nietzsche called people “vicious animals”, and Jean-Jacques Rousseau in “Discourses on Inequality”[3] argued that people have an innate goodness that is corrupted by society. Rousseau's statement can be seen as contrary to the religious concept of original sin and subsequent salvation by faith. Immanuel Kant's views on the existence of good and evil in man are also unique. He believed that human nature is inherently evil and includes a tendency to do evil. However, man has positive qualities, and moral education should be aimed at eliminating these tendencies. Many philosophers say that man is naturally inclined towards goodness, and those who choose evil in their lives are deviations from the norm, they are exceptions. Good and evil in the world can be compared to health and illness: those who choose good are morally healthy, and those who embrace evil suffer from moral decay and deformation of character.

“Good” and “evil” are moral concepts that serve as the main indicators of a person’s morality and reflect the polarity of thoughts, feelings and actions. They are closely related to a person’s spiritual experience, which determines their quality. These categories serve as the basis for the development of a system of ethics and moral values. Good is a moral concept that expresses the positive

meaning of events in relation to a high ideal as the highest value. Everything that deviates from the moral ideal and leads to immorality is called evil.

V.S. Solovyov argues that moral virtue includes actions performed with a sense of duty and is universal in nature. In his opinion, moral virtue is defined by reason as truth or the fulfillment of obligations. Moreover, everything that benefits a person is good. Ideally, good and virtue are inseparable, and the latter is a direct, universal and necessary consequence of the first, representing the undoubted expediency and effectiveness of good.

Therefore, good is considered as the absolute and relative basis of individual existence. In an absolute sense, good means the eternal and true perfection of humanity. It is realized as a possibility in human consciousness and as a reality in the historical process of social development. In a relative sense, kindness is the expression of goodwill towards others.

“Evil” and “good” are related to each other for the following reasons: 1) they know each other through their mutual existence; 2) it is impossible to resist evil without understanding good. These are opposing forces that influence their own existence by denying their own existence. The concepts of “good” and “bad” are of great importance in the field of ethics, which studies moral principles and standards of behavior. These concepts serve as basic categories that allow us to distinguish between good and evil, morally acceptable and unacceptable. Good is usually defined as something desirable, useful, and morally upright. It is associated with the concepts of justice, mercy, honesty and nobility. Also, goodness is a symbol of harmony, happiness and prosperity for everyone.

In contrast, evil is defined as something that is undesirable, harmful, and morally wrong. It is associated with ideas of violence, cruelty, selfishness and injustice. Evil causes pain, misery and destruction. Definitions of good and evil may vary depending on cultural, religious and moral beliefs. However, some common features help to understand their essence. The concepts of good and evil can be subjective and open to different opinions and interpretations. They are often the subject of debate, because everyone has their own idea of what is good and what is bad. For example, some people may view the death penalty as a cruel practice, while others may view it as necessary to ensure public safety.

The outcome of good and evil affects both individuals and society as a whole. Good deeds can lead to personal well-being, happiness and social harmony. On the contrary, participation in evil acts inevitably leads to harm, suffering and destruction. That is why the pursuit of good and avoidance of evil is the most important task of every person.

It is important to understand that good and bad qualities can be complex and multifaceted. They are influenced by many factors such as culture, education, religion and personal beliefs. Therefore, in the field of ethics, it is important to analyze and discuss these concepts in order to develop moral consciousness and make informed decisions in our lives.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the concepts of “good” and “bad” are deeply and complexly interconnected. By philosophically analyzing the relationship between good and evil, we can try to expand the scope of justice and maximize welfare.

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